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ABSTRACT

Biometrics, which refers to identifying an individual based on his or her physiological or behavioral characteristics, has the capability to reliably distinguish between an authorized person and an imposter. Signature verification systems can be categorized as offline (static) and online (dynamic). This paper presents neural network based recognition of offline signatures system that is trained with low-resolution scanned signature images using Radon Transform with Genetic Algorithm. The signature of a person is an important biometric attribute of a human being which can be used to authenticate human identity. However human signatures can be handled as an image and recognized using computer vision and neural network techniques. With modern computers, there is need to develop fast algorithms for signature recognition. There are various approaches to signature recognition with a lot of scope of research. In this paper, off-line signature recognition & verification using neural network is proposed with Random Transform and Genetic Algorithm, where the signature is captured and presented to the user in an image format and with the help of Radon Transform we extract total feature of signature and these features are train using neural network. Signatures are verified based on parameters extracted from the signature using various image processing techniques. The Off-line Signature Recognition and Verification is implemented using Image Processing and Neural Network Toolbox Matlab Software. This work has been tested and found suitable for its purpose.

KEYWORDS: Offline Signature Recognition; Radon Transform; Back Propagation Neural Network (BPNN) and Genetic Algorithm.

INTRODUCTION

Signatures are most legal and common means for individual's identity recognition and verification since people are familiar with the use of signatures in their daily life. A signature is a unique identity of a person. Therefore we are in great need to develop a system which can recognize signatures. A signature verification system decides whether a given signature belongs to a claimed owner or not. A signature recognition system, on the other hand, has to decide a given signature belongs to which one of a certain number of writers. Signature recognition is split into two according to the available data in the input. Offline (static) signature recognition takes as input the image of a signature and is useful in automatic recognition of signatures found on bank checks and documents. Online (dynamic) signature recognition uses signatures that are captured by pressure sensitive tablets that extract dynamic properties of a signature in addition to its shape.

Offline systems are of interest in scenarios where only hard copies of signatures are available where as in online systems most of the features are extracted at the time of signing. So the offline signature recognition is more challenging. Therefore, in offline signature recognition methods, less information is available than online methods. Offline signature recognition primarily focus on the visual appearance of our signature for recognition purposes, Signature Recognition examines behavioral aspects that manifest themselves when we sign our name. Therefore it is essential to recognize the signatures with high accuracy

The written signature is regarded as the primary means of identifying the signer of a written document based on the implicit assumption that a person's normal signature changes slowly and is very difficult to erase, alter or forge without detection. The handwritten signature is one of the ways to authorize transactions and authenticate the human identity compared with other electronic identification methods such as fingerprints scanning and retinal vascular pattern screening. It is easier for people to migrate from using the popular pen-and-paper signature to one where the handwritten signature is captured and verified electronically. The signature of a person is an important biometric attribute of a human being and is used for authorization purpose. Various approaches are possible for signature recognition with a lot of scope of research. Here, we deal with an off-line signature recognition technique. Signatures are composed of special characters and flourishes and therefore most of the time they can be unreadable. Also intrapersonal variations and interpersonal differences make it necessary to analyze them as complete images and not as letters and words put together. Signature recognition is the process of verifying the writer's identity by checking the signature against samples kept in the database. The result of this process is usually between 0 and 1 which represents a fit ratio (1 for match and 0 for mismatch). Signature recognition is used most often to describe the ability of a computer to translate human writing into text. This may take place in one of two ways either by scanning of written text (off-line method) or by writing directly on to a peripheral input device. The first of these recognition techniques, known as Optical Character Recognition (OCR) is the most successful in the main stream. Most scanning suites offer some form of OCR, allowing user to scan handwritten documents and have them translated into basic text documents. OCR is also used by some archivist as a method of converting massive quantities of handwritten historical documents into searchable, easily-accessible digital forms.

OVERVIEW OF SIGNATURE RECOGNITION

A problem of personal verification and identification is an actively growing area of research. The methods are numerous and are based on different personal characteristics; voice, lip movement, hand geometry, face, odor, gait, iris, retina and fingerprint are the most commonly used authentication methods. All these psychological and behavioral characteristics are called biometrics. The driving force of the progress in this field is above all, the growing role of the internet and electronic transfers in modern society. Therefore considerable number of applications is concentrated in the area of electronic commerce and electronic banking systems.

The biometrics have a significant advantage over traditional authentication techniques (namely passwords, PIN numbers, smart cards etc) due to the fact that biometric characteristics of the individual are not easily transferable are unique of every person and cannot be lost, stolen or broken. The choice of one of the biometric solutions depends on several factors which include:

- User acceptance
- Level of security required
- Accuracy
- Cost and implementation time

The method of signature verification reviewed in this paper benefits the advantage of being highly accepted by potential customers. The use of the signature has a long history which goes back to the appearance of writing itself. Utilization of the signature as an authentication method has already become a tradition in the western civilization and is respected among the others. The signature is an accepted proof of identity of the person in a transaction taken on his or her behalf. Thus the users are more likely to approve this kind of computerized authentication method. Signature verification systems differ in both their feature selection and their decision methodologies. More than 40 different feature types have been used for signature verification. Features can be classified into two major types: local and global. Global features are features related to the signature as a whole, for instance the average signing speed, the signature bounding box and Fourier descriptors of the signatures trajectory. Local features correspond to a specific sample point along the trajectory of the signature. Examples of local features include distance and curvature change between successive points on the signature trajectory. Most commonly used online signatures acquisition devices are pressure sensitive tablets capable of measuring forces exerted at the pen-tip, in addition to the coordinate of the pen. The pressure information at each point along the signature trajectory is another example of commonly used local feature. Some of these features are compared in order to find the more robust ones for signature verification purposes. Other systems have used genetic algorithms to find the most useful features. Due to the high sampling rate of the tablet, some consecutive sample points may mark the same trajectory point especially when the pen movement is slow.

Most verification systems resample the input so as to obtain a trajectory consisting of equidistant points. This is often done in order to remove redundant points to speed up the comparisons and to obtain a shape-based representation, removing the time dependencies, separately keep track of the local velocity values and use them in aligning two signatures. Signature recognition and verification involves two separate but strongly related tasks: one of them is identification of the signature owner, and the other is the decision about whether the signature is genuine or forged. Also, depending on the need, signature recognition and verification problem is put into two major classes: (i) On-line signature recognition and verification systems (SRVS) and (ii) Off-line SRVS. On-line SRVS requires some special peripheral units for measuring hand speed and pressure on the human hand when it creates the signature. On the other hand, almost all Off-line SRVS systems rely on image processing and feature extraction techniques.

Image Preprocessing and Features Extraction

We approach the problem in two steps. Initially, the scanned signature image is preprocessed to be suitable for extracting features. Then, the preprocessed image is used to extract relevant geometric parameters that can distinguish forged signatures from exact ones using the ANN approach.

Preprocessing:

The signature is first captured and transformed into a format that can be processed by a computer. Now it's ready for preprocessing. In preprocessing stage, the RGB image of the signature is converted into grayscale and then to binary image. The purpose of this phase is to make signatures ready for feature extraction. The preprocessing stage includes two steps: Color inversion, Filtering and Binarization.

Color Inversion:

The true color image RGB is converted to the grayscale intensity image by eliminating the hue and saturation information while retaining the luminance.

Fig.1. (a) A sample signature to be processed; (b) A Grayscale Intensity Image

A grayscale image is a data matrix whose values represent intensities within some range where each element of the matrix corresponds to one image pixel.

Image Filtering and Binarization:

Any image when resample is filtered by a low pass FIR filter. This is done to avoid aliasing. This aliasing occurs because of sampling the data at a rate lower than twice the largest frequency component of the data. So a lowpass filter will remove the image high frequency components. And for this purpose the filter used. Now the grayscale image is segmented to get a binary image of objects. In a binary image, each pixel assumes one of only two discrete values: 1 or 0. A binary image is stored as a logical array.

Fig.2. Binary Image interpreting the bit value of 0 as black and 1 as white

Features Extraction is the key to develop an offline signature recognition system. We use a set of five global features that cannot be affected by the temporal shift.

Types of Signature Verification

Based on the definitions of signature, it can lead to two different approaches of signature verification.

Off-Line or Static Signature Verification Technique

This approach is based on static characteristics of the signature which are invariant. In this sense signature verification, becomes a typical pattern recognition task knowing that variations in signature pattern are inevitable; the task of signature authentication can be narrowed to drawing the threshold of the range of genuine variation. In the offline signature verification techniques, images of the signatures written on a paper are obtained using a scanner or a camera.

On-line or Dynamic Signature Verification Technique

This is the second type of signature verification technique. This approach is based on dynamic characteristics of the process of signing. This verification uses signatures that are captured by pressure sensitive tablets that extract dynamic properties of a signature in addition to its shape. Dynamic features include the number of order of the strokes, the overall speed of the signature and the pen pressure at each point that make the signature more unique and more difficult to forge. Application areas of Online Signature Verification include protection of small personal devices (e.g. PDA, laptop), authorization of computer users for accessing sensitive data or programs and authentication of individuals for access to physical devices or buildings.

Nature of Human Signature

It is supposed that the features of the process of signing originate from the intrinsic properties of human neuromuscular system which produces the aforementioned rapid movements. Knowing that this system is constituted by a very large number of neurons and muscle, fibers is possible to declare based on the central limit theorem that a rapid and habitual movement velocity profile tends toward a delta-log normal equation. This statement explains stability of the characteristics of the signature. Thus, the signature can be treated as an output of a system obscured in a certain time interval necessary to make the signature. This system models the person making the signature.

Randon Transform

The radon function computes projections of an image matrix along specified directions. A projection of a two-dimensional function $f(x, y)$ is a set of line integrals. The radon function computes the line integrals from multiple sources along parallel paths, or beams, in a certain direction. The beams are spaced 1 pixel unit apart. To represent an image, the radon function takes multiple, parallel-beam projections of the image from different angles by rotating the source around the center of the image. The following figure shows a single projection at a specified rotation angle.

Genetic Algorithm

Genetic Algorithm (GA) An evolutionary algorithm which generates each individual from some encoded form known as a "chromosome" or "genome". Chromosomes are combined or mutated to breed new individuals. "Crossover", the kind of recombination of chromosomes found in sexual reproduction in nature, is often also used in GAs. Here, an offspring's chromosome is created by joining segments chosen alternately from each of two parent's chromosomes which are of fixed length. GA is useful for multidimensional optimization problems in which the chromosome can encode the values for the different variables being optimized.

METHODOLOGY

To verify the effectiveness (qualities and robustness) of the proposed Signature Recognition we conduct several experiments with this procedure on several images. The methodology of our proposed work is given below:

Phase 1: Firstly we develop a particular GUI for this implementation. After that we develop a code for the loading training dataset of signature image.

Phase 2: We develop the code for the feature extraction using Randon Transform for training dataset. After that apply Genetic Algorithm for feature reduction and train all extracted feature using neural network.

Phase 3: we develop a code for the loading test signature image for the testing purpose.

Phase 4: we develop a code for preprocessing using Radon Transform for feature extraction of test sample of signature. After that we apply Genetic algorithm for feature reduction of test image.

Phase 5: we develop a code for Neural Network Classification for the simulation purpose of test feature and recognition of signature.

CONCLUSION

In this paper we propose “Offline Signature Recognition System Using Radon Transform with Genetic Algorithm”. Offline signature is one of the most widely accepted personal attributes for identity verification of the person. The written signature is regarded as the primary means of identifying the signer of a written document based on the implicit assumption that a person’s normal signature changes slowly and is very difficult to erase, alter or forge without detection. The handwritten signature is one of the ways to authorize transactions and authenticate the human identity compared with other electronic identification methods such as fingerprints scanning and retinal vascular pattern screening. It is easier for people to migrate from using the popular pen-and-paper signature to one where the handwritten signature is captured and verified electronically. Here we Use Genetic Algorithm for the feature reduction purpose. The average recognition accuracy from 90% to 99%. We use training set of 500 persons. False reject rate reduce, false acceptance rate increase and equal rate reduce.

REFERENCES

- [1] S. A. Angadi, Smita Gour, Gayatri Bajantri "Offline Signature Recognition System Using Radon Transform" 2014 Fifth International Conference on Signals and Image Processing 978-0-7695-5100-5/13 \$31.00 © 2013 IEEE DOI 10.1109/ICSIP.2014.1356 2014 Fifth International Conference on Signal and Image Processing
- [2] D. Zhang, J. Campbell, D. Maltoni, and R. Bolle. Special issue on biometric systems. *IEEE Trans. Systems, Man and Cybernetics - C*, 35(3):273–275, 2005.
- [3] K. Bowyer, V. Govindaraju, and N. Ratha. Introduction to the special issue on recent advances in biometric systems. *IEEE Trans. Systems, Man and Cybernetics - B*, 37(5): 1091–1095, 2007.
- [4] Ashwini Pansare, Shalini Bhatia "Handwritten Signature Verification using Neural Network" International Journal of Applied Information Systems (IJ AIS) – ISSN : 2249-0868 Foundation of Computer Science FCS, New York, USA Volume 1– No.2, January 2012
- [5] Nilesh Y. Choudhary, Mrs. Rupal Patil, Dr. Umesh. Bhadade, Prof. Bhupendra M Chaudhari "Signature Recognition & Verification System Using Back Propagation Neural Network" International Journal of IT, Engineering and Applied Sciences Research (IJ EASR) ISSN: 2319-4413 Volume 2, No. 1, January 2013
- [6] A.I. Al-Shoshan. Handwritten signature verification using image invariants and dynamic features. *Proc of the IEEE Int Conf on Computer Graphics, Imaging and Visualization (CGIV'06)*, 2006.
- [7] M. Piekarczyk. Hierarchical random graph model for off-line handwritten signatures recognition. *IEEE Int Conf on Complex, Intelligent, Software Intensive Systems*, 2010.
- [8] S.M.S. Ahmad, A. Shakil, M.A. Faudzi, R.M. Anwar. Analysis of 'goat' within user population of an offline signature biometrics. 10th IEEE Int Conf on Information Science, Signal Processing and their Applications (ISSPA 2010).
- [9] J.P. Drouhard, R. Sabourin, and M. Godbout. A neural network approach to off-line signature verification using directional PDF. *Pattern Recognition*, 29(3), (1996), 415--424.
- [10] M. Arathi and A. Govardhan, Member, IACSIT "An Efficient Offline Signature Verification System" International Journal of Machine Learning and Computing, Vol. 4, No. 6, December 2014
- [11] K. Delac and M. Grgic. A survey of biometric recognition methods. *Proc of 46th IEEE Int Symposium Electronics, Croatia*, 184-193, June 2004.
- [12] B. Kovari, Z. Kertesz, and A. Major. Off-line signature verification based on feature matching. 11th IEEE Int Conf on Intelligent Engineering Systems, Budapest, Hungary, 29 June - 1 July 2007.
- [13] A. Kholmatov and B. Yanikoglu. Identity authentication using improved on-line signature verification method. *Pattern Recognition Letters*, Volume 26, Issue 15, November 2005, pp. 2400-2408.

- [14] T.S. Ong, W.H. Khoh, A. Teoh. Dynamic handwritten signature verification based on statistical quantization Mechanism. IEEE Int Conf on Computer Engineering and Technology, 2009.
- [15] J. Edson, R. Justino, F. Bortolozzi, and R. Sabourin: "An off-line signature verification using HMM for random, simple and skilled forgeries," Proc. Sixth Int. Conf. Document Analysis and Recognition, pp. 1031-1034, Sept. 2001.
- [16] B. Zhang, M. Fu and H. Yan: "Handwritten signature verification based on neural 'Gas' based vector quantization", IEEE Int.Joint Conf. on Neural Networks, pp. 1862-1864, May 1998. verification using compression networks and positional cuttings", Proc. 2003 IEEE Workshop on Neural Networks for Signal Processing, vol. 1, pp. 627-636, 2003.
- [17] A. Chalechale and A. Mertins: "Line segment distribution of sketches for persian signature recognition", IEEE Proc. TENCON, vol. 1, pp. 11-15, Oct. 2003.